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City of Novi Sad ambient air: Toxic elements (metal(loid)s) associated health risk

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Ambient air can be a source of exposure to toxic elements (metal(loid)s). The study aimed to investigate (metal(loid)s) composition of the inhalable fraction of particulate matter (PM₁₀, diameter up to 10 µm) and assess human health risks. 1074 PM₁₀ samples were gathered at five monitoring sites (basic-rural/urban, urban/suburban-traffic, industrial) in the City of Novi Sad during 2023. The content of lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), arsenic (As), and nickel (Ni) was determined after microwave digestion and ICP-MS determination.

The overall share of the samples with quantified amounts of elements was 90.5% Pb > 86.3% As > 38.5% Cd > 26.2% Ni. The highest mean concentrations (ng/m³) over the monitored period were recorded at suburban traffic (Pb 7.9, Cd 0.2, As 1.3) and industrial sites (Ni 3.4). The elements' averaged concentration (ng/m³) order was as follows: Pb 5.9 > Ni 3.0 > As 1.2 > Cd 0.2. The mean hazard index ranged from 0.23 on basic-rural to 0.34 on industrial sites, with a mean of 0.31, revealing no health risk. The elements' contribution (%) order was as follows: Ni 76.3 > As 24.9 > Cd 6.2 > Pb 0.5. Carcinogenic risk for children and adults ranged from 8.1E-07 to 1.0E-06, with a mean of 9.4E-07, and from 3.2E-06 to 4.0E-06, with a mean of 3.8E-06, respectively, indicating low risk. The element with the highest contribution was As (76.6%).

Given the high probability of exposure to toxic metal(loid)s through multiple sources (air, food, and water), recorded levels of risk indicators related to inhalation exposure are not enough to ensure the protection of human health.

Keywords: air monitoring, arsenic, lead, PM₁₀, public health, risk assessment

References

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